

as being pasted on the pictures. But while reading the book, these forms—as forms on the pictures—are ignored, and instead, the viewer looks across (or through) them and into the pictures. For non-naive readers, such mental gymnastics are part and parcel of perceiving pictures in picture-books.

Sometimes these mental calisthenics involve almost Einsteinian manipulations of space and time. Flip through Sendak's *In the Night Kitchen*. Sometimes there is one picture per page. Other times one picture runs across two pages. The maximum is four events per page. The temporal sequence is usually from left to right; but it also may be from top to bottom—or a combination of both. Nevertheless, we seldom get lost. Now, isolate any picture in one of the scenes where Mickey is falling: notice that it is *prima facie* meaningless out of its temporal and spatial context. Specifically think about the mental exercise employed in comprehending the sequence involving Mickey in the milk. He dives in the bottle, swims to the top (in the left picture), and (in the right picture) pours a cup of milk into the batter; but these two "pictures" (really two events) depicted only one milk bottle, and are separated by only a vertical

white line down the middle of the page. Yet we perform the correct mental acrobatics when viewing the picture and shuffle the sequence into the correct order of space and time. Is not this mental manipulation remarkable?

"However automatic our first response to an image may be," writes E. H. Gombrich, "its actual reading can never be a passive affair" (86). But how often are we aware of this? And when made aware, can we ever again accept crude theories about the passivity of perception? The cognitive psychologist Ulric Neisser curtly put it this way: "we can see only what we know how to look for . . ." (20). If the perception of our environment is an active probing of visual possibilities, then how much more must be the visual understanding of the two-dimensional array offered by pictures?

Children's picture-books supply an almost limitless sources of examples to support the active theory of picture-perception. Indeed, I hope the examples presented here will suffice to make clear the principle that comprehending the content and meaning of a picture is a mental process drawing upon prior knowledge of concepts. It is therefore essential to take a fresh look at the

relationship between pictures and texts. It is not enough simply to assert, as Cianciolo does, that "Illustrations in books can help the reader to create visual images and help him to go beyond the printed word" (95). Surely, some pictures can. But most cannot.

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Of Nakedness and Children's Books

Perry Nodelman

In *Ways of Seeing*, John Berger modestly quotes a conventionally-minded art professor's huffy comment about how "John Berger manages to interpose himself . . . between us and the visible meaning of a good picture" (107). Berger proves to my satisfaction that the professor is wrong about the painting in question; but the professor is right about Berger. After reading Berger's discussions of pictures, I can't see them the way I did before. And while I don't particularly like seeing the aspects of pictures that Berger points out to me, I believe that they are there to see, and that being able to see them is important.

Pictures are things to look at, whenever we feel like looking at them. Looking at them should give us pleasure, and if it doesn't, we have every right to dismiss them. These are truisms; but after reading Berger's *Way of Seeing*, I find myself unable to take them for granted. Instead, I am tempted to consider the implications of my own language. What if, in these sentences that so accurately describe pictures, I assumed that pictures were people? I would have to conclude that the kind of people they are is the kind called prostitutes.

If I did, I would be noticing something interesting about the act of looking at a picture. It is always an act of supremacy—of having power over something. The viewer is always making use of the picture on his own terms and for his own pleasure; the picture is always being used, and it is only satisfactory to a viewer if it gives him what he wants or likes. Those are facts, but not necessarily significant ones; they are equally true of most of the physical objects in our lives. But Berger makes use of these simple facts to develop a persuasive theory of seeing.

For people interested in children's picture books, it's particularly significant that Berger's theory begins with the idea that all art is illustration. There is always a vast gulf between what we see and what we can say about what we see: "each evening we see the sun set. We know that the earth is turning away from it. Yet the knowledge, the explanation, never quite fits the sight" (7). Consequently, pictures, which are records of what people see or have seen, always make sense only in terms of the words used to explain them. In this way, all pictures demand and depend on words—the words of their names or their captions, the words the artist used as he tried to formulate his theory of art, the words evoked by

conventional images like death's heads and naked little boys with wings.

Berger's fear is that we often attach the wrong words to pictures, particularly pictures from other periods:

If we "saw" the art of the past, we would situate ourselves in history. When we are prevented from seeing it, we are being deprived of the history which belongs to us. Who benefits from this deprivation? In the end, the art of the past is being mystified because a privileged minority is striving to invent a history which can retrospectively justify the role of the ruling classes, and such a justification can no longer make sense in modern terms (11).

As this quotation makes clear, Berger's position is radically political; he wants to make us see implications of pictures that we would otherwise take for granted, lest they co-opt our values and attitudes without our even being conscious that they are doing so. To be conscious of those meanings is to be radicalized in the truest sense of the word—to recognize how ideas and values that we might prefer to despise become rooted in our unconscious.

The best example of the insidious means by which pictures communicate attitudes we might not want to share is Berger's discussion of the sort of

traditional European painting that we think of as being realistic. This sort of realism assumes that reality is what one can see from one fixed point in space: "perspective makes the single eye the centre of the visible world. Everything converges on to the eyes as the vanishing point of infinity. The visible world is arranged for the spectator as the universe was once thought to be arranged for God" (18). Not surprisingly, such pictures do tend to put their viewers into godlike positions; as I suggested earlier, when we look at them we look freely at what there is to see, we take our pleasure in the perusal of what has been put on display for us. According to Berger, what we see in traditional paintings merely mirrors conventional societal attitudes—in particular, attitudes towards the differences between men and women:

A man's presence is dependent upon the promise of power which he embodies. If the promise is large and credible his presence is striking A man's presence suggests what he is capable of doing to you or for you By contrast, a woman's presence expresses her own attitude to herself, and defines what can and cannot be done to her Her own sense of being in herself is supplanted by a sense of being appreciated as herself by another One might simplify this by saying: *men act and women appear*. Men look at women. Women watch themselves being looked at (45-47).

That was once true is incontrovertible; that it still continues to be true, at least in the world shown us by pictures, is confirmed by even a brief glance at the advertisements in any popular magazine. Despite the revolution in attitudes of the last decade, they still almost always show men doing things without any apparent consciousness that anybody might be looking at them, and women standing still, face forward, smiling, inviting us to look at them; men still act, women still appear.

The implications of the way pictures have traditionally depicted men and women differently—and still continue to do so—are particularly clear in pictures of people without their clothes on. A standard polite view is that nakedness is obscene, but that nudity is art; consequently, great artists depict nudes, and pornographers depict naked people. But for Berger, nakedness is mere simple fact, whereas many of the great paintings of nudes and pornography have much in common, and are equally distasteful. For him, the whole point of pictures of nudes is that they imply their viewer—and that their viewer exercises his right to power when he enjoys them. In all paintings of nudes, "there remains the implication that the subject (a woman) is aware of being seen by a spectator" (49). Consequently,

In the average European oil painting of the nude the principal protagonist is never painted. He is the spectator in front of the picture and he is presumed to be a man. Everything is addressed to him. Everything must appear to be the result of his being there. It is for him that the figures have assumed their nudity. But he is, by definition, a stranger with his clothes still on (54).

In such paintings, the subject smiles out at us, puts herself on display, and encourages us to enjoy the way she looks. Of a picture of Nell Gwyn commissioned by her lover King Charles II, Berger says, "This nakedness is not . . . an expression of her own feelings; it is a sign of her submission to the owner's feelings or demands" (52). Such paintings reflect the attitudes of the societies that commissioned and enjoyed them; by not seeing them for what they mean, we both misunderstand history and preserve attitudes that ought to be left to history.

As I suggested earlier, the pictures in popular magazines still convey those theoretically outmoded attitudes. As we might expect, the ones intended for men, like *Playboy*, are filled with pictures of nude women, and I assume that they are most often looked at by clothed men. And as Berger's analysis of the visual depiction

" . . . pictures in popular magazines . . . convey . . . theoretically outmoded attitudes."

of women in history might suggest, the magazines intended for women are also filled with pictures of women—increasingly, nowadays, in magazines like *Vogue* and *Cosmopolitan*, nude women. In these magazines, women are still understood to be creatures to be looked at. Men are expected to find women most "beautiful" when most exposed and most available, and women are still expected to look at themselves in terms of how they are supposed to expect men to look at them.

Nowadays, of course, there are exceptions. We have been liberated. There are magazines for women like *Playgirl* which shows pictures of naked men in the traditional poses of female nudes. And there are fashion features in men's magazines like *Playboy*, and even whole magazines for men like *Gentleman's Quarterly*, which show pictures of men in the traditional poses of female models. Ironically, however, these magazines do not free either men or women from the old patterns of visual domination. As *Playgirl's* articles on fashion make clear, both men and women are still supposed to think of women as objects to be looked at. In the *Playgirl* I looked at recently (November, 1983), the fashion feature was supposed to

be about clothes, but the pictures showed men looking adoringly at women as the women looked adoring out of the pictures at me; and as Berger says of the European tradition, "It is true that sometimes a painting includes a male lover. But the woman's attention is very rarely directed towards him. Often she looks away from him or she looks out of the picture towards one who considers himself her true lover—the spectator owner." (56) *Plus ça change . . .*

But astonishingly, magazines for men also encourage men to think of themselves as creatures to be looked at, creatures who can dress up prettily to excite the interest of those more powerful than themselves; the sex of those more powerful viewers is, perhaps deliberately, left unclear. The *Playboy* I bought along with *Playgirl* (also November, 1983) contained the usual old diet of female nudes, but also, four ads for bodybuilding equipment featuring the muscular torsos of hunks, one of them titillatingly caught in the act of pulling his shirt over his head in provocative high definition lighting; and the fashion feature showed women looking adoringly at men while the men looked adoringly at me.

Meanwhile, *Playgirl* encourages women to think of themselves as powerful dominators with the right to view men as passive creatures available for perusal; the men in these pictures may be muscular, but that their minds are unthreatening is made clear by copy that tells us they work on construction sites or that "I want to get into cosmetology"—just like those big-bosomed dingbats who display their all in *Playboy*. *Playgirl's* fantasies are stories about female lawyers who excite male illiterates into bursts of great passion. *Playgirl's* horoscope assures Scorpio that men fear her and Sagittarius that her, yes, *her* "first house of ego is bulging with planetary action, and . . . your cockiness is enormous." A typical *Playgirl* perfume advertisement shows an aggressive-looking woman, fully clothed, dripping with aggressively metallic ornaments, and with her hand planted masterfully on the head of a naked, vacant-looking boy/man, accompanied by the instruction, "Conquer your heroes." Given the absence of clothes in the pictures of males, it's clear who wears the pants in *Playgirl*. Apparently, we have had a visual revolution that frees neither men nor women from the attitudes of visual dominance; instead, we can now all be dominators together.

The pictures of *Playgirl* are particularly interesting when seen in Berger's terms. He claims that in traditional paintings, especially those that show women holding mirrors as they admire themselves, "The surveyor of woman in herself is male; the surveyed female. Thus she turns herself into an object—and most particularly an

object of vision: a sight" (47). We might ask, then, what happens when women turn men into objects, sights, like the sights of nude men in *Playgirl*. The answer is that they treat them as men have traditionally treated women in such pictures: as representations of the viewer's power. The men in *Playgirl* are like the female nudes of traditional painting—frequently supine, always at ease and inactive, they make enticingly kittenish pouts at the viewer. They rarely smile or seem to be in control; their expressions are inviting, but not aggressive. They seem to say, "look at me, admire me, I am on view for your pleasure." They display none of the aggressive dominance traditionally associated with male sexuality. Perhaps most significantly, while their penises are almost always in full view, they are not threatening; unlike the male nudes of both hetero- and homosexual pornography, these un-macho hunks almost never have erections.

At first glance, that has little to do with children's books; be patient, for I intend to try to persuade you that it does. Meanwhile, it clearly does have a lot to do with the values and attitudes of female children—particularly those about to embark on their teenage years. It has a lot to do with that complicated subject simply because of the astonishing similarity between the unclothed men of *Playgirl* and the partially clothed men depicted in popular magazines like *16* and *Bop*.

The almost singleminded subject of such magazines is adoration of the young men who appear in youth-oriented TV shows and movies. If you are not twelve and female, you are not likely even to be able to guess the last names of the Johns and Bruces and Toms whose first names are emblazoned on their covers. But within the covers of these magazines, these Johns and Bruces and Toms are demigodlets, superstars of the first order. There are stories about having dates with them: "I went home on cloud nine, my head filled with dreams of John." There are stories about their vital statistics; according to *Bop* (November, 1983), Tommy's shirt size is "Medium (Perfect to show off those great shoulders!)" and his eyes are "Hazel . . . one gaze and you're a goner." You can enter contests for their used shirts: "Just imagine! This green T-shirt, snuggled so warm and close to Bruce's beautiful body, could be hanging in your closet—or better still, you could be wearing it yourself!" You can, in fact, you must, adore these guys. The cover of *Tigerbeat Star* (November 1983) quotes Chris as saying, "I love to be desired!"

The pictures of Chris and John and Bruce are quite astonishingly alike. They show the particular young hunk in question, most often with his shirt off or

open, and wearing tight jeans. His long, usually blonde hair is gently tousled, his full lips are parted (although more in a Playmate pout than a smile), and his inevitably long lashes hood his dreamy eyes as he stares into the camera. Any fool could figure out that these are sexy pictures. But like the *Playgirl* nudes, these pictures imply anything but traditional masculine sexual aggressiveness. The image is more Marilyn Monroe than John Wayne. With their long lashes and full lips, these are boys who look like girls.

In actual fact, they are not boys at all. They are men. The copy tells us they are twenty-one or -two or even older, even though they look much younger. And perhaps most interestingly, they almost never have any body hair. None at all. Somebody has quite clearly been at work with either a razor or an airbrush, for twenty-two year old men are rarely quite so totally hairless as these twenty-two year old boys are. But in his discussion of traditional oil paintings, Berger points out an interesting phenomenon:

in the European tradition generally, the convention of not painting the hair on a woman's body Hair is associated with sexual power, with passion. The woman's sexual passion needs to be minimized so that the spectator may feel he has the monopoly of such passion. Women are there to feed an appetite, not to have any of their own (55).

It's not hard to see that similar factors operate in terms of the way young girls are encouraged to look at the hairless men of *Tigerbeat*.

Their doing so might even be useful, therapeutic; for *Tigerbeat* does, I suppose, allow young girls to explore their awakening sexuality safely, by allowing them to fantasize about cute guys who are actually comfortably far way in Hollywood, actually unobtainable. Maybe *Tigerbeat Star* is right in claiming that John "wants to get close to you"; but he's not likely to do it. In that way, John is unlike the pimply and disturbingly actual guy who sits in the next row to you in math class, a guy who is close enough and excitable enough to actually maybe try something, and who is probably in the process of growing real hair on his body. Teen magazines offer a safe expression of sexuality by making the objects of sexual fantasy safely unobtainable and also, safely unmasculine, safely passive, boys who look and act like girls.

But I wonder. I wonder if encouraging young girls to admire the unthreateningly passive bodies of famous young men, bodies which are unavailable in fact but thoroughly available for one's visual pleasure, is anything more than an underhanded appeal to the pleasures of domination. I wonder if that pleasure is

ever really therapeutic. Teen magazines heaved into view before *Playgirl* did—is it possible that all those sixties pictures of David Cassidy and the other girlish boys of earlier days paved the way for November's "hot new find" in *Playgirl*, a twenty-two-year old man with as much hair on his chest as Marilyn Monroe or David Cassidy? Maybe. In any case, I'm a little disturbed by the fact that, while twelve-year old girls read teen magazines and get to admire the bodies of male superstars, twelve-year old boys tend instead to read comic books, and get to admire the exaggeratedly muscular bodies of male superheroes in skintight superhero suits. I mean, why do we expect children of all sexes to enjoy looking at the bodies of men?

So what does this have to do with children's books? Well, for one thing, the young girls who like looking at the pictures in *Tigerbeat* might find them comfortingly familiar in relation to childhood memories. These androgynous naked torsos are surprisingly like the figures depicted in some of the most famous of children's illustrations. I've always sensed a curiously sexless sensuality in the work of those late Victorian and early twentieth century illustrators of gift books that are highly touted as the old masters of children's book art. After reading Berger, I think I have a clearer sense of what that sexless sensuality is all about.

Berger says, "What distinguishes oil painting from other forms of painting is its special ability to render the tangibility, the texture, the lustre, the solidity of what it depicts. It defines the real as that which you can put your hands on" (88). Whether or not they are oil paintings, the pictures of Arthur Rackham and Kay Nielsen and Edmund Dulac are filled with richly ornamented surfaces that imply richness, and that postulate the value of what one can put on hands on—rich materials and other material things. Berger sees traditional paintings of such things as evidence of capitalist values: "such a painting is a demonstration of more than the virtuosity of the artist. It confirms the owner's wealth and habitual style of living" (99). And again, "Oil painting, before it was anything else, was a celebration of private property. As an art-form it derived from the principle that *you are what you have*" (139). In a real sense, the gift books that Dulac's and Rackham's pictures appeared in were evidence of such wealth; they were always expensive. Appropriately, they encourage us to look at the rich things they depict as things to possess, to have the power to own. And the people in them are things to possess also—frequently androgynous and passive, Tigerbeatish girl-boys of another age.

In David Larkin's *The Fantastic Kingdom*, a collection of representative works of this type, Maxfield Parrish's illustration for Marvell's "The Garden" (plate 11) might be either a breastless girl or a surprisingly soft boy; the pipes he holds tell us he is probably Pan, and therefore male. Whereas Rackham's grotesques often seethe with energy, his pretty heroes and heroines are mirror images of each other. His Rhine Maidens have the sexless bodies of long distance runners (Larkin, plate 6), while a dragon-fighter (plate 8) has sharply defined sinews but breasts at least as large as the Rhine maidens's. But Kay Nielsen's nudes are the most sexless. The male-or-maybe-female creature who illustrates "When the Cock Crowed" (Larkin, plate 32) is invitingly supine, like a *Playboy-or-Playgirl* centerfold; Nielsen's North Wind takes a more aggressive stance, but his torso is teenagish, and his nipples are a pair of unflinchingly red asterisks (plate 26). None of the faces accompanying any of these naked bodies reveal any character—or indeed, any expression. And all unaggressively naked bodies are like the lavishly ornamented fabrics surrounding them—things to own, things made available for our viewing pleasure, things we enjoy because they are costly and we have the power to look at them. They appeal to our lust for power rather than our sexuality; or rather, like *Playboy* and *Playgirl* and *Tigerbeat*, they replace real sexual passion with the pleasure of domination.

The gift-book tradition of children's books for grownups continues. The most frankly pornographic picture I've seen recently is in a collection of folk tales rewritten by Richard Adams. Even when they theoretically depict violent motion, all of Yvonne Gilbert's pictures in this book have a static deadness that allows viewers to focus on a suffocating richness of the details; and her illustration of a giant eel's fascination with a Polynesian sky goddess depicts the goddess floating languidly in absolute passivity as fronds of seaweed lasciviously caress her full frontal nudity.

In more recent children's books, nakedness is not often depicted. When it is depicted, however, Berger's ideas about nudity come into play, and reminiscences of *Playgirl* are evoked, more often than makes me comfortable.

Consider, for instance, children's books about how babies are born. They often depict naked babies. But the naked babies are almost always male babies. In Gunilla Wolde's *Emma's Baby Brother*, the picture showing the baby's diaper being changed makes it graphically clear that he's male; in Paul Showers' *A Baby Starts to Grow*, the doctor holds up a male infant, and even in Sara Bonnett Stein's *That New Baby*, which is illustrated by photographs, the new baby

in the photographs is male. I have a theory about this. My theory is that we are so used to thinking of naked females as nudes that the only way we can look at a naked body innocently, without overtones of sexual titillation, even a baby's body, is to make the body a male body. Even then, one can't be sure of the absence of titillation. Jessie Wilcox Smith's illustration for "He felt how comfortable it was to have nothing on him but himself" from *The Water Babies* (Larkin, plate 1) shows a presumably male baby in a pose familiar to early *Playboy* pinup afficianados—supine, with his knee coyly lifted to mask his presumed maleness. I suppose this is an appropriate illustration for a sentence that echoes Berger's idea that, because nudes are naked for the benefit of viewers, "nudity is a form of dress" (54).

According to Berger, "Almost all post-Renaissance European sexual imagery is frontal—either literally or metaphorically—because the sexual protagonist is the spectator-owner looking at it" (59). That the naked young bodies in picture books are not without sexual significance is made clear by the almost total absence of female frontal nudity in the entire history of the genre. In his interview with Jonathan Cott, Maurice Sendak says, "I had a picture showing a girl with her vagina in full view in *The Light Princess*, and nobody made a fuss about that, which makes me think the whole world is male chauvinist—vaginas don't count" (55). But I think they do count; I suspect the point is that we have categories to account for female nakedness in pictures, and therefore don't find it surprising, even in children's picture books. But unfortunately, the category we have to account for it is the category nude, so that even unclothed female children are almost inevitably pinups. Nevertheless, Sendak's naked light princess is a clear exception. She is neither smiling nor pouting nor in repose with her eyes closed, as female and male nudes almost always are; in fact, she looks a little pixilated, a little like Red Skelton's depiction of the widdle kid. Her moronically crazy face makes it clear that, while she may have no clothes on, that doesn't make her into a pinup. Maybe that's why nobody has cared to be upset by her.

But before *Tigerbeat* and *Playgirl*, we had no categories equivalent to the nude or the pinup for the depiction of male nakedness. Consequently, illustrators have been able to depict naked boys in picture books without being charged with pornographic intentions. When Maurice Sendak's Mickey revealed his all on his visit to the Night Kitchen, there was much controversy; but the controversy surrounded the question about whether penises should be on view at all in

children's books, not the question about whether the particular depiction was meant to be sexually enticing. People did not expect little girls to be turned on by Mickey's equipment; they expected them to be surprised and, ideally, horrified by it. Boys can be naked without their clothes on, whereas traditionally, naked girls are nude; so boys can quite naturally and unprovocatively have penises in picture books. Thomas has one in Gunnilla Wolde's *Thomas Takes a Bath*. Simon has one in Carlos Friere's illustrations for Daniel Wood's *No Clothes*. David has one in Sendak's illustrations for Randall Jarrell's *Fly by Night*.

But hardly any full frontal nudity for females, even though no-one complained about Sendak's light princess. Girls sit in bathtubs, or wear towels round their middles, or hide behind trees, just like their ancestresses used to do in a certain sort of semi-modest girlie-painting. Again, I suspect this difference in the treatment of boys and girls exists because we unconsciously acknowledge that any depiction of a female body is like a pin up. In fact, the only relatively well-known illustration of a totally naked young girl I know is decidedly pinup-like. Carl Larsson's "Bedtime Scene," reproduced in William Feaver's *When We Were Young* and even on postcards, shows a young girl in nothing but black stockings, facing the viewer. The stockings look like leather boots. The girl is decidedly nude; she stands and looks at us without modesty, her pout exactly the same as the one pouted by November's *Playgirl* centerfold; she clearly knows we are looking at her and that we have a right to do so, and I suspect she wants to be a cosmetologist when she grows up. I find this picture embarrassing; I'm not sure I do have the right to look at a child in these terms. I suspect that picture book artists avoid depictions of female nakedness simply because it is so hard not to turn female nakedness into traditional nudity. It took the genius of Sendak to give us a naked female baby who looks drunk rather than nude.

Lately, there have been at least two other attempts. I'm happy to report that in Camilla Jessel's *The Joys of Birth*, published in 1982, there is finally a photograph of a female newborn, as well as photographs of male ones; they are equally unsexy, maybe because, as we should have known all along, infants aren't conscious enough to make themselves available to a viewer's implied presence. Meanwhile, Maurice Sendak, who pioneered full frontal nudity for males in *In the Night Kitchen* and for females in *The Light Princess*, has done it again for the girls in *Outside Over There*—again without controversy and without sexiness. The goblin baby whose undeniable femininity

is revealed in *Outside Over There* is too busy dancing to Ida's wonderhorn to look very enticingly available; anyway, she looks more like a dour-faced dowager than a playmate.

Meanwhile, the pictures of naked boys also all show them clearly doing something—moving, active, *not* posing. Wolde's Thomas is dumping water on some flowers during his moment of truth, and despite the full frontal nudity, Friere's Smon's elbows and knees and heels have cartoon action lines, to show he's in motion and not merely available for inspection. As for the forerunner, Sendak's Mickey: a picture of a naked boy with his hands aggressively on his hips as he howls "COCK a DOODLE DOO!" may be a little suggestive, but it ain't no centerfold. Sendak's own comments on this, in his interview with Jonathan Cott, are singularly appropriate: "adults will take their kids to museums to see a lot of peckers in a row on Roman statues and say: That's art, dearie, and then come home and burn *In the Night Kitchen*" (54). Whether Sendak realizes it or not, the picture of Mickey crowing is not art, at least not in the sense that the Roman statues are art. The statues are nude, and Mickey is just plain naked.

But the other pictures of the naked Mickey in *In the Night Kitchen* might in fact be art, dearie. They give little sense of movement, and have little energy. They show Mickey floating through the air, asleep, so that we can look at him without his being conscious that anybody might be doing so; we can, in fact, take advantage of him. The same seems to be true of Sendak's pictures of Jarrell's David, and these carefully observed pictures of a boy asleep are closer to traditional cheesecake than any of the other pictures in this group. Sendak told Jonathan Cott that he made David naked because he looked silly in pajamas. Maybe so; but one feels a little like a voyeur, checking out the sleeping David's exposed nakedness without his permission; at least the hunks in *Playgirl* pout at us to let us know they know we're looking. Cocky Mickey never deserved those felt-marker diapers librarians used to draw on him, but maybe David could use some.

Incidentally, the naked male body in repose and unconscious of a viewer seems to be a favorite subject of Sendak's: not just Mickey and David, but also, Mr. Rabbit splendidly in the buff in *Mr. Rabbit and the Lovely Present* as he lies on a green hillside, his eyes closed. Mr. R. is one of the few animals in picture books who can talk to humans but who does not own a jacket, and this scene of him as a nude centerfold sitting beside a clothed girl is almost a reversal of "Dejeuner sur L'herbe," that famous painting by Manet that shows a naked woman at a picnic with

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clothed men; in fact, this sensuous rabbit takes up pinup poses throughout the book, (and I believe that helps create the fascinating tension that Sendak brings to Charlotte Zolotow's undistinguished story.)

The differences between males and females are preserved even in less graphic depictions of childlike nakedness. There are numerous books about children taking baths. In almost all of them, boys gallivant and girls pose. The tradition goes back as far as Caldecott, who illustrates "When I was a Farmer, a Farmer's Boy" with a picture of a naked boy horsing around on nurse's knee while a pouty-mouthed nude girl sits quietly in the tub, her voluptuous back awaiting our inspection. More recently, Sami Suomalainen shows Jule Ann smiling sensuously as she gets her back scrubbed in Robert Munsch's *The Mud Puddle*, while Michael Martchenko shows Munsch's boy of *The Boy in the Drawer* smiling devilishly in a tub and then exploding from it tempestuously. When Ginette Anfousse's Jojo takes a bath in *The Bath*, she splashes around a little—but always while she's staring at the viewer, putting on a show for us; in John McKee's pictures for Dennis Lee's *The Ordinary Bath*, the boy in the tub is too busy dealing with Armageddon to even know we're looking at him.

In fact, the most significant thing Berger's ideas let us see in picture books is the difference between pictures of children who know they are being observed and who make themselves observable, and pictures of children who simply get on with the business at hand, whatever that business may be. Not surprisingly, and even when they have clothes on, the observables, the would-be pinups, are always female, the others usually male.

It's something of a convention for picture book illustrators to depict the main character of a story on the cover, smiling at us in a sort of portrait. But when Ray Cruz depicts Judith Viorst's *Alexander, Who Used to Be Rich Last Sunday* on the cover, he shows him in a pose that sums up the book: grimacing over his empty pockets. Meanwhile, Ben Shecter's *Hester*

the Jester is about a liberated girl who wants an unusual job for a female; even so, she smiles out at us in a fashion model pose on the cover as she shows off her jester's hat. The liberation here does not extend to the implications of the visual imagery. In fact, as Berger suggests in his discussion of the paintings of peasants by Franz Hals, such smiles imply the servility of the subject in relation to the implied viewer:

pictures of the poor . . . are reassuring. Here the painted poor smile as they offer what they have for sale. (They smile showing their teeth, which the rich in pictures never do.) They smile at the better-off—to ingratiate themselves, but also at the prospect of a sale or a job. Such pictures assert two things: that the poor are happy, and that the better-off are a source of hope for the world (104).

Hals' peasants are like nudes to the extent that their faces have become costumes—masks they wear for the benefit of those who have the right to look at them. Apparently, poverty and femininity are strange bedfellows.

That the girls of picturebooks know they are subservient, and therefore creatures who must smile at those who have the right to look at them, becomes particularly clear in books that depict both boys and girls together. Presumably, the boys and the girls are involved in the same actions; but more often than not, the boys are involved in the action, while the girls smile out at the viewer. The cover of Shirley Hughes' *Lucy and Tom's Christmas* shows Tom looking in his Christmas stocking, while Lucy sits on the bed and smiles at us. At the end of John Burningham's *Mr. Gumpy's Outing*, the animals, the boy, and Mr. Gumpy concentrate on their tea: the girl smiles at the viewer. The most disconcerting example of girls being aware of their viewers is Terry Furchgott and Linda Dawson's *Phoebe and the Hot Water Bottles*. Phoebe smiles at us on the cover. She smiles at us on the title page. She smiles at us on the first page of the text. She smiles at us when she takes her hot water bottles for a walk, and again when she teaches them how to swim, in a pool filled with children of both sexes who don't seem to have the vaguest idea we can see them. One might well assume that, since the pictures in picture books are illustrations, they will depict the characters performing the actions of the story. But Phoebe is like a bad actress in an amateur play, conscious of her audience and unable to stop flirting with it.

It might be significant that all these examples of would-be female pinups are from British books. Perhaps Americans are more liberated. On the other hand, I

couldn't easily find American books that depicted boys and girls playing together; and I could find a lot of books about girls in which the girls smile at their viewers. In fact, I found so many of them in my favorite children's bookshop that I bet the manager that the cat depicted smiling seductively at us from the cover of a book would turn out to be a female cat. I won the bet. Furthermore, the last page of the American Susan Jeffers' *Hansel and Gretel* shows Hansel hugging his father, his back towards us; while Gretel is also hugging, she has her faced turned toward us and is smiling at us.

In fact, the girls in contemporary illustrated versions of fairy tales often take the poses of pinups. Trina Schart Hyman's *Snow White* has a centerfold's pouty mouth, and Hyman takes every opportunity to show her supine, passive and available; Jeffers also gives us two views of a supine *Snow White*, and both she and Nancy Eckholm Burkert give us *Snow White's* mother framed by a window, a pretty sight to admire. Hyman's *Sleeping Beauty* smiles at us invitingly and coyly over her shoulder, and when her prince comes upon her, the picture is set up so that he can see only her back, while we may peruse the full glory of her beauty in passive sleep. All of this, I believe, is as it should be; these pinup poses are accurate illustrations of these stories, for these traditional heroines of another time are passive, are primarily notable for their beauty, do make themselves available to admiring viewers even within the stories themselves. They are real-life pinups.

But when the young girls of other sorts of picture books assume similar poses, I am not ready to forgive their artists. To quote Berger again, "The contradiction can be stated simply. On the one hand the individualism of the artist, the thinker, the patron, the owner: on the other hand, the person who is the object of their activities—the woman—treated as a thing or an abstraction" (62). As long as the

girls of picture books continue to be conscious of our presence as viewers, we will not be free of the idea that they are things—things like the girls of *Playboy* and the men of *Playgirl* and *Tigerbeat*.

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The American Super-hero Comic Strip: True Descendant of Italian Renaissance Art

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I want to make an art historical case for super-hero comics, those "sixty-cent dreadfuls" which proclaim in gaudy colors the improbable adventures of semi-nude muscle-men and ladies with outlandish names like *Thor*, *Daredevil*, *Spider-Man*, and *Wonder-Woman*. I believe that the artistic style of these books, even when presented in bad taste, nonetheless follows

the great innovations of Italian Renaissance painting: the very ideas of Giotto, Masaccio, Leonardo da Vinci, Raphael, Michelangelo, and Caravaggio which initiated not only an artistic but a perceptual revolution that affected the way people have defined "reality" ever since.

I am aware that the "adventure comic," as it is called in the trade, is generally regarded a weed in the garden of children's literature. It was first introduced in the

1930's, becoming especially virulent after *Superman* was born in a periodical called *Action Comics* in 1938. In spite of the fact that early copies of this are now worth more than a Dickens first edition, parents in my social circle would never think of comparing the comics to the "educational" illustrated stories for children of the sort that are regularly applauded in the *ChLA Quarterly*. If some parents do begrudgingly allow their offspring to read this "trash,"